

quadridentate behaviour of the ligand). Thus in the sky-blue (II), greenish-yellow (IV) and orange-yellow compound (III), we have successfully unfolded the neutral, monobasic and dibasic characters of the quadridentate Schiff base (I) respectively.

Experimental

The ligand acetylacetone *bis* (benzoyl-hydrazone) and the complex (II) were prepared according to the procedures of our previous work¹.

Physical measurements

Nickel(II) was estimated as *bis* (dimethylglyoximate) nickel(II). Nitrogen was determined by Duma's method. The chloride was determined as silver chloride, and magnetic moment was obtained from corrected χ_M value, using a Gouy balance with $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a calibrant. Nujol mull spectra were run by R. S. I. C., Madras. C, H, analyses as also the IR spectra were carried out by C. D. R. I., Lucknow.

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A Mixed Anion Salt of Beryllium

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In past few years many mixed ligand complexes of metals have been studied by different physico-chemical methods. Potentiometric evidences are available for the formation of 1:1:1 M(II)AB ternary complexes¹⁻⁸ where A is usually EDTA and B a secondary ligand like glycine, salicylic, succinic, tartaric or maleic acid. Survey of the literature

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however, reveals that ternary complexes without the involvement of EDTA have been studied once⁴. The present paper describes the formation of BeAB system where A is an anion of 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) and B of chromotropic acid (CTA).

DNS⁵ and CTA⁶ figure prominently in the discussion of hydroxy carboxylic acids and hydroxy acids respectively. Each of DNS and CTA provides two possible interaction sites.

Experimental

Beryllium sulphate, potassium nitrate, sodium hydroxide (all AnalaR grade), Reidel's DNS and disodium salt of CTA (E. Merck) were used. Solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A Cambridge bench type pH meter was used for pH measurements.

To know the stoichiometry of the Be-DNS & CTA complex, the proton displacements were evaluated titrating solutions containing Be and the concerned ligands in different ratios employing a standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves are shown in figure. Curve

Figure. : Potentiometric titration curves of CTA, DNS and of both in the absence and presence of Be employing 0.1 M NaOH.

- Curve 1, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA ;
 Curve 2, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS ;
 Curve 3, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS ;
 Curve 4, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ Be ;
 Curve 5, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS + $1.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ Be.

1 shows only one inflection at $m=1$ which is due to neutralisation of one of the two phenolic-OH groups

of CTA ($R' \begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \\ \diagup \\ \text{OH} \end{matrix}$). The second phenolic -OH is not neutralised due to the formation of intramolecular H-bonding⁷. Curve 2 shows two inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ which indicate the neutralisation of -COOH and -OH groups of DNS ($R \begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \\ \diagup \\ \text{COOH} \end{matrix}$).

When 1 : 1 mixture of these ligands is titrated against a standard alkali, two inflections at $m=1$ and $m=3$ (Curve 3) are observed which confirms the above neutralisation patterns. When equimolar concentration of Be is added to a 1 : 1 mixture of these ligands, an inflection at $m=4$ (Curve 4) is observed which reveals the formation of a 1 : 1 : 1 mixed anion salt as under

The formation of such a salt is confirmed by the observation that on titration with an alkali a 1 : 1 : $\frac{1}{2}$, DNS, CTA, Be mixture shows an inflection at $m=3.5$.

The reaction may be represented as follows :

The formation of this salt appears to justify the 4-fold coordination requirements of the sp^3 hybridised Be.

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Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Mn(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone-*o*-tolil (HCBOT)

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In continuation of our previous communications^{2,3} herein, we describe potentiometric studies on chelates of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone-*o*-tolil (HCBOT) with Mn(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) in 60% v/v dioxan water media at $\mu = 0.1M$ at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Experimental

The expanded scale pH meter of systronic with a wide range (0.01 pH glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone-*o*-tolil was synthesised by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with orthotoluidine. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 157°-159°.

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. The potentiometric titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere using carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution and the constant ionic strength was maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solution. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{4,5} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹ has been applied to determine the protonation constants of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log K values were computed by various computational methods as summarised in Table 1.